

USING LAPTOPS IN A CLASSROOM

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Abstract:

This survey provides information about using of various gadgets such as laptops, telephones, computers and other in school classes, which are common in almost all countries today. Humans mainly scholars are facing the fact that today's modern technologies especially gadgets are making life easier. A host of collage and universities students can utilize laptops during classes in order to gain more source of knowledge and expand their worldview. There are several negative and positive effects of using a laptop for young students. The article first considers the negative and positive aspects of using gadgets during learning processes. Afterthat, the professors' opinions are reflected about the topic. At last deduces with a summary.

Key words: Internet, gadgets, classroom, laptop, technology, education, collage, apps, university.

Introduction.

Today we live in the age of modern technology. People are using all type of the technologies they need. This makes life easier. Young people in particular are using many methods that are convenient for them to gain knowledge. For example they are using the internet to learn a lot of necessary information during their educational processes. With the rise of digital learning tools, education platforms and access to vast resources online laptops offer students a way to enhance their learning experience. There are some opinions that universities should provide with laptops for students with a wireless connection to the internet.

Advantages of using a laptop in a classroom.

Laptops have become a device that everyone uses today. We can know its various advantages. For instance laptops are compact and lightweight, making them easy to carry around. This allows for flexibility in working from different locations, whether at home, at cafe, at class or while travelling. Laptops provide students with immediate access to a wealthy of information online, making it easier to research topics, view educational videos, and access academic resources during lessons. Investigating student attention, meditation, cognitive load, and satisfaction during lectures in a foreign language supported by speech enable language translation [Informa UK Limited]. It has been proven that success can be achieved through the use of computers and laptops during educational processes. [Alexandar 2004] , [Campbell et al., 2003] , [Wagner 2005] , [Demb et al ., 2004] , [Ilacqua et al., 2007]. Students can use different learning apps, digital tools in order to understand complex concepts such as calculators, note taking apps.

One of the survey report that having a laptop in class is helpful for their academic performance, with note-taking cited as the most important benefit [Kay and Laurialla 2014]. Teachers can integrate multimedia such as videos, animators and interactive lessons which can make learning more engaging and help students understand difficult concepts more easily. This will give scholar a broader understanding of the topic. Laptops can facilitate communication between students and teachers through email, message apps, or learning management systems, helping clarify doubts and providing instant feedback.

Some drawbacks of using laptops.

There are a host of drawbacks of using laptops during classroom. The temptation to multitask, such as checking emails or browsing the internet can hinder students' ability to pay attention to lectures or class discussions. [Mayer and Morena 2003].

In addition electronics usage is distracting to neighboring students. A number of surveys cleared that texting is distracting to nearby students [Tindell and Bohlander 2011]. Grace Martin and Gay Said that the downside of using laptop during class. [Grace Martin, Gay 2001; Fried 2008]. Prolonged use of laptops can cause eye strain, poor posture and other physical issues especially when students do not use ergonomic setups. More screen time can affect students' mental health too and well-being as they may experience stress or difficulty sleeping due to overexposure to screens. Unforeseen problems like software crashes, connectivity issue or battery problems can disrupt the learning process. Students may be busy with this kind of troubles. Instead of time which spent for them student should pay attention to their study. By this way they can achieve their purposes. Some students may not have an understanding of how to use a computer which can cause

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them difficulty. The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill "support a laptop requirement that will reach 15000 undergraduates by fall 2003". UNC has formed an association with Cisco Systems for a wireless laptop environment.

Summary.

In classroom the use of laptops is still in its early stage. More and more colleges and universities are entailing that they need computer, laptops and these kinds of technologies during classes. However few faculty members have problems understanding computers and using them in their daily life. This paper endeavors to bring some positive aspects of using laptops during classroom too. It can be beneficial for both students and teachers. They provide quick access to information enable digital learning tools and enhance productivity through note-taking and research. However, laptops can also be distracting if not used properly leading to a lack of focus on the lesson. Therefore, while laptops can be valuable educational tools, they should be used thoroughly to ensure they contribute positively to the learning environment.

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